

Keeping the Elderly Safe: Economic Crisis and Quality of Care

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The negative impact of the economic crisis on population health has been studied from the demand-side perspective. However, few studies addressed the influence of economic shocks on patient health outcomes as a result of the healthcare delivery. In Italy, deteriorating economic conditions required hospitals to undertake cost-containment measures which could have led to delivery of substandard quality and compromised patient safety.

Methods & Results: We analyse the impact of adverse economic conditions on geriatric patients' safety, focusing on elderly people who are frequent users of hospital care. The key contribution is the computation and analysis of patient safety measures, which are usually overlooked by researchers in favour of conventional mortality indicators, while compromised patient safety may negatively impact patients health thereby imposing significant human and economic costs on the health system.

We proxy the economic situation by utilizing local unemployment rates at a "Sistema Locale del Lavoro" (SLL) level, which aggregates all neighbouring towns with common economic structure. We take advantage of the fact that the crisis affected different areas in Italy in varied intensities, translating into comparatively low and high unemployment rates depending on the area. Hence, our study will exploit the geographic heterogeneity in both the timing and intensity of the crisis to analyse if worsening of the economic conditions was associated with more adverse patient safety outcomes.

On patient safety side, we will focus on health outcomes for elderly patients that were admitted to hospitals and underwent surgical interventions. We will use secondary diagnosis and procedure codes to compute a number of safety indicators related to avoidable hospital-associated adverse conditions, such as pressure ulcers, in-hospital falls with hip fractures, pulmonary embolism and deep vein thrombosis, as well as a set of peri- and postoperative measures, including hematoma, sepsis, acute kidney injury and respiratory failure.

We will employ the dynamic panel data methodology to investigate the relationship of interest. In particular, we will use the generalized method of moments and fixed effect estimation techniques and conduct the analysis at SLL level.

Finally, we aim to conduct a cross-country comparison by using the corresponding data for Portugal to assess how economic shocks brought on by the economic crisis affected the quality of hospital care in these two countries that share similarities in their health systems, but differed in terms of the intensity of undertaken austerity measures.

Discussion: The findings may be of interest to policymakers and inform healthcare stakeholders on the relationship between adverse economic conditions and health of vulnerable populations.